

Online Marketplace & Client Management System

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APPROVAL

The project entitled Paper “**Online Marketplace & Client Management System**” submitted by Rehnumah Taslim Munmun, Reg. no: 19502004253 to the Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Ahsanullah Institute of Information and Communication Technology, Dhaka, Bangladesh has been accepted as satisfactory for the partial fulfillment of the requirement for the degree of Bachelor of Science in Computer Science & Engineering approved as to its style and contents.

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DECLARATION

We hereby, declare that the work presented in this project “**Online Marketplace & Client Management System**” is the outcome of the investigation performed by under the supervision of **Sayem Islam Shohag**, Lecturer of CSE Department, Ahsanullah Institute of Information and Communication Technology, Dhaka, Bangladesh. We also declare that no part of this project and thereof has been or is being submitted elsewhere for the award of any degree or diploma.

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ABSTRACT

The project “**Online Marketplace & Client Management System**” is a web-based software program that will help both creative agencies/freelancers and their clients/buyers to get connected for the purpose of providing/availing required services. For creative agency/freelancer, it will be more efficient and easier to provide their service to their customer. They will be able to schedule their meetings, get updates quickly about their projects, get invoices, and many more great features which will be time-saving for both client and service provider. It is more secure and less expensive than the existing system. The client will get all the project updates frequently. It is more secure in hiring someone from our platform. Through our platform, anyone can hire freelancers to do work in areas such as graphic & multimedia, mobile apps, e-commerce & software development, writing, and data entry right through to engineering, sales and marketing, accounting, and legal services. Our marketplace allows both local & global clients to post projects and hire. They will be able to compare other sellers’ services prices and will be able to find the best one according to their budget.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

HTML	Hypertext Markup Language
CSS	Cascading Style Sheets
PHP	Hypertext Preprocessor
DFD	Data Flow Diagram
ER	Entity Relationship
JS	JavaScript
RAM	Random Access Memory
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
DNS	the Domain Name System
URL	Uniform Resource Locators
CDN	Content Delivery Network

Chapter-1

Introduction

1.1 Overview

Our Project is web-based “**Online marketplace & Content management system**”, where buyer can buy services from seller. A seller can also manage their clients through this site. This web-based application is mainly for **Creative Agencies/Freelancers** and **Client/Buyer**. By using this site, they will be able to avail or purchase require services. The main target of this project is to create an international marketplace for **Agency/Freelancers. Online Marketplace and Client Management System** is designed for connecting with client, setting up meetings, projects progress tracking, more secure order method, authorized seller and buyer.

1.1.1 What is Online Marketplace

An online marketplace is a type of e-commerce website, where product or service information is provided by multiple third parties. In an online marketplace, consumer transactions are processed by the marketplace operator and then delivered and fulfilled by the participating retailers or wholesalers. These types of websites allow users to register and sell single items to many items for a "post-selling" fee.

1.1.2 What is CMS

A Client Management System is a **software application that keeps track of individual relationships between a business and each of its customers**. Sales, marketing, and support teams often refer to data in the Client Management System to establish and nurture customer relationships so that they become loyal clients.

Every customer is important. The more opportunities a customer has to connect with your business, the better. CMS help ensure customers' needs are met by allowing businesses to gain more insight into their behavior and modify their operations accordingly. After implementing CMS software, your business will be able to recognize the value of each and every customer. The more you know about your customers, the more their needs will be met, and the more your sales will grow.

1.1.3 Why do you need a CMS

Whether you are a small business or an enterprise, your goal is to expand and win more clients. While you need new customers, existing clients are the greatest asset of any company. They already know you, trust you, are in business with you, and contribute to your revenue. In fact, Gartner estimates that 80% of a company's future revenue will come from 20% of its existing customers. This makes every client an integral part of your company, and it is crucial to understand, nurture, and build a good relationship with them to gain their loyalty.

Knowing how to nurture that relationship requires in-depth knowledge about their requirements and every interaction they've had with your business. But this information is spread across tools—spreadsheets, phone, email, notes, calendars, etc.

As you get more customers, organizing and managing reliable information and having instant access to it becomes a struggle.

You'd require a tool that can show the complete details about clients with context, communication history, and keep you updated about appointments, notes, and insights. And that's what a client management software does.

1.2 Objectives of the project

The main goal of this project is to get a secure platform where freelancer/creative agency will be able to manage their clients project efficiently and increase their sales and revenue. On the other hand, buyer/client will be able to get their required services.

The other objectives are –

- Increases level of trust between seller and the buyer.
- Provides greater transparency.
- Time Saving.
- Opportunities for overseas sales.

1.3 Application of the project

Online marketplace is a place where many skilled freelancers works. They mainly work project based or hourly based. Anyone can buy services from this site. Sellers can manage their clients order and buyers can get update easily about their projects progress. Freelancers can work from

any side of the world and get paid. Buyers can compare and choose anyone from the marketplace according to their budget.

1.4 Benefit

- **Organized Information**

With your client information organized in a straightforward and customizable manner, you can easily keep track and access everything you need to be more efficient.

- **Better Collaboration**

The tool acts as a single source of truth for the marketing and sales teams. No information gaps, no going back and forth. The customer always hears a consistent voice from you.

- **Higher Revenue**

With a well-rounded view of your customers at all times, you can cross-sell and up-sell at the right moments, with higher success rates.

- **Faster Buying Process**

Buyers can spend less time in buying their services for what they want. They can easily browse through many sellers' services at a time and buy what they like.

- **No Reach Limitations**

Buyers can buy services from any country's seller without any restriction. As they can reach anyone from any country, the seller gets the chance to reach more customer. Sellers that need to expand their reach to find new customers can benefit from this.

Chapter 2

Existing System

2.1 Existing System

There are many existing systems like “**Online Marketplace and Client Management System**”. They are –

- **Upwork**
- **Fiverr**
- **Freelancer**
- **Belancer**

2.1.1 Upwork

Upwork, formerly **Elance-oDesk**, is an American freelancing platform. In 2015, the Elance-oDesk merger was rebranded as Upwork and the company's full name is now Upwork Global Inc. Upwork is currently based in Santa Clara and San Francisco, California.

In 2017, Upwork had over twelve million registered freelancers and five million registered clients. More than three million jobs worth over \$1 billion USD together were posted in 2017.

Upwork is a kind of Client Management System. It is also a marketplace where buyer and Freelancer/ Creative Agency connect together and avail their required service. Here buyer post their job or project with all the requirement and seller/freelancer/Creative Agency bids for the Project. After bidding buyer checks their proposal and hires someone who is fit for the job. Sometime they select them after an interview which conduct through a video call. Buyer hires freelancers both hourly and project-based payment condition. From every projects payment it cuts 20% from the main price of the service.

Upwork allows clients to interview, hire and work with freelancers and freelance agencies through the company's platform. The client posts a description of their job and a price range they are willing to pay for a freelancer to complete it. The client may invite specific freelancers to apply for their jobs, or else post the job for any freelancer who is interested to apply. Once the client has chosen who they want to complete the job, they hire that

freelancer by sending a contract with set hours, pay rate, and a deadline for the work to be completed.

2.1.2 Fiverr

Fiverr is an Israeli online marketplace for freelance services.

Fiverr serves to allow listing and applying for small one-off jobs, or *gigs*, online. Jobs listed on the platform are diverse and range from "get a well-designed business card" to "help with HTML, JavaScript, CSS, and jQuery". Fiverr is a company built on the model of listing temporary work positions. Freelancers work in a variety of workplaces, ranging from home to office. Fiverr serves as e-commerce platform to freelancers and companies to sell their services by using their gigs. The pricing of Gigs depends on how much a seller earns per completed task.

Fiverr is also a kind of Client Management System. It is a marketplace too, where buyer and Freelancer/ Creative Agency connect together and avail their required service. Here seller offers many kinds of services through their gigs also there is a buyer request option where buyers can post their job or project details and seller sends request to get that job/projects work. From every projects payment it cuts 20% fee from the seller's account. Fiverr was founded by Micha Kaufman and Shai Wininger. The founders came up with the concept of a marketplace that would provide a two-sided market for people to buy and sell a variety of digital services typically offered by freelance contractors. Services offered on the site include writing, translation, graphic design, video editing and programming. Each service offered is called a "gig". Fiverr's services start at US\$5, and can go up to thousands of dollars with gig extras.

2.1.3 Freelancer

Freelancer is an Australian freelance marketplace website, which allows potential employers to post jobs that freelancers can then bid to complete. Founded in 2009, its headquarters is located in Sydney, Australia.

Freelancer is a marketplace where employers and employees are able to find each other. The site allows employers to post work for site members who place bids in a competitive tender process. The site also allows members to host and enter contests for which prize money is offered as a reward. Freelancers and employers develop profiles on the site as

they offer, win and complete work and write and receive reviews of people they work with or for. The site's members receive a finite number of bids to use on the site, which are periodically replenished. A series of account options are offered, ranging from free accounts through to professional subscriptions.

Freelancer takes a 10% fee, which can be reduced with paid monthly membership, with a minimum fee of \$5. The company has recently announced its new move into home and local services, staying first in its home market of Australia.

2.1.4 Belancer

Belancer is a Bangladeshi online marketplace where companies and freelance professionals connect and collaborate remotely. Local companies or organizations and people can buy and sell services such as design, online marketing, writing, web & mobile app development & any other online-based service. The payment will be made via local payment gateways. Bangladesh is a rapidly developing Next Eleven emerging economy and one of the Frontier Five markets. Belancer.com is the first online works freelancing Marketplace and Expert Hub in Bangladesh, any Local or Global Employer can Post Project in any category i.e. Web, Mobile & Software Development, Design & Multimedia, Admin, Writing & Translation, Sales & Marketing and so on to receives 100s of proposal to compare in a min and chat with bidder & select, pay via safe online payment when employer 100% satisfied. Bangladesh is one of the top ten global online outsourcing destination. belancer.com is first and largest outsourcing marketplace in Bangladesh.

2.2 Limitation

In the existing system there are lots of limitation. For example, Fiverr doesn't provide any video call meeting services to every freelancer. It doesn't have a live time work progress checking system. The payment system takes minimum 15 days to clear the payment. Both Upwork and Fiverr takes 20% commission from the seller and also takes extra fee from the buyer.

2.3 Disadvantage of Existing System

- No order request system
- High rate commission fee
- Video call service is not available for all
- Project progress tracking is not enhanced
- Delays to clear the payment
- Dashboard is not organized
- Invoice system is not organized

2.4 Comparison

Features	Online Marketplace & Client Management System	Fiverr	Upwork	Freelancer	Belancer
Order Request	√	X	X	X	X
Commissions%	8%	20%	20%	20%	10%
Video Calling Feature for all	√	X	√	X	X
Free Version	√	√	√	√	√

Table 1: Comparison between “Online Marketplace & Client Management System” and the related systems

Chapter 3

System Design

3.1 Features

Main features of our project are-

- Order Request Method
- Low Commission
- Projects Progress Tracking
- Secure Payment Method
- Setting up Meetings
- Authorized Seller and Buyer

3.1.1 Order Request Method

In existing system, a buyer can just simply place an order and the seller don't get the chance to negotiate the price of the work. Cause some buyers places order with minimum budget and the work requires away more than the order price. On that case if the seller cancels the order, his profile gets a bad impression which is not good for his ID. It scales down the reach of his profile to the customer and for that his sales number decreases. So, we came up with the feature call **Order Request**. This feature will help the seller to accept the order or deny it or send a request to increase the budget. And with this there will be no effect on the profile. So, they won't face any problem to reach their organic customer.

3.1.2 Low Commission

As we know existing system Fiverr & Upwork takes a huge number of commissions from sellers and buyer for every order, It's really too much for any freelancer. So, we offer a service where the commission will be half of that 20% commission.

3.1.3 Projects Progress Tracking

Now it will be easy for buyer to keep the project progress in track with more detailed information.

3.1.4 Secure Payment Method

A secure payment system, or SPS, refers to payment processing and information services that provide users' security online. An SPS is a type of payment processing that ensures a user's financial and personal information is protected from fraud and unauthorized access.

3.1.5 Setting Up Meetings

We know **Fiverr** doesn't allow every seller to connect with buyer through Call. So, we keep the feature where seller will be able to contact with the buyer through video call which will help them to discuss the project more openly. That will make a good connection between them and also seller will have more information about the project. As we know human can express more by speaking rather than writing.

3.1.6 Authorized Seller and Buyer

We will allow only verified customer and seller in our platform so you will get every Authorized seller. There will be no chances to be not paid or not getting the file.

3.2 Work Process

To get started with our system both buyer/client and Creative Agency/ Freelancer needs to be had an account on our website. Account creating process is very simple. Anyone can open an account. They will just need an email to open an account. To start working or placing an order both buyer and seller needs to be verified by submitting their NID CARD.

3.3 Technologies used in this project

3.3.1 WordPress

WordPress is a free, open-source website creation platform. On a more technical level, WordPress is a content management system (CMS) written in PHP that uses a MySQL database. In non-geek speak, WordPress is the easiest and most powerful blogging and website builder in existence today.

WordPress is an excellent website platform for a variety of websites. From blogging to e-commerce to business and portfolio websites, WordPress is a versatile CMS. Designed with usability and flexibility in mind, WordPress is a great solution for both large and small websites.

3.3.2 HTML

HTML is the standard markup language used to create web pages. Web browsers can read HTML files and render them into visible or audible web pages. HTML elements form the building blocks of all websites. HTML allows images and objects to be embedded and can be used to create interactive forms. It provides a means to create structured documents by denoting structural semantics for text such as headings, paragraphs, lists, links, quotes and other items.

3.3.3 CSS

Is a Web page derived from multiple sources with a defined order of precedence where the definitions of any style element conflict? The Cascading Style Sheet, level 1 recommendation from the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C), which is implemented in the latest versions of the Netscape and Microsoft Web browsers, specifies the possible style sheets or statements that may determine how a given element is presented in a Web page. And describes how HTML elements are to be displayed on screen, paper, or in other media.

3.3.4 PHP

Is an open source server-side language which is used for creating dynamic web pages. It can be embedded into HTML. PHP is usually used in conjunction with a MySQL database on Linux/UNIX web servers. It is probably the most popular scripting language. And it is a widely-used general-purpose scripting language and interpreter that is freely available. A full explanation of all the PHP tags.

3.3.5 MySQL Database

MySQL is the world's most popular open source database. With its proven performance, reliability and ease-of-use, MySQL has become the leading database choice for web-based applications, used by high profile web properties including Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, Yahoo! and many more.

3.4 Data Flow Diagram (DFD)

Context-Level DFD

Figure 1: Context Level Data Flow Diagram

DFD For Admin

Figure 2: Data Flow Diagram for Admin

DFD For Seller

Figure 3: Data Flow Diagram for Seller

DFD For Client

Figure 4: Data Flow Diagram for Client

3.5 ER Diagram

Figure 5: Entity Relationship (ER) Diagram

3.6 Use Case Diagram

Figure 6: Use Case Diagram

Chapter 4

Design

4.1 Introduction

Design section is the section where anyone can easily understand the whole system or the part of it. Its emphasis on translating design specification to performance specification is system design.

4.2 Hardware Requirement

- Processor
- Ram
- Hard Disk
- Monitor

4.3 Software Requirement

- Operating System
- Database
- Language
- Compatible Browser

4.4 Workflow

Figure 7: Iterative Waterfall Model Diagram

Chapter 5

System Requirement

5.1 Hardware

- PC
- Processor
- RAM

5.1.1 PC

Personal computer (PC), a digital computer designed for use by only one person at a time. A typical personal computer assemblage consists of a central processing unit (CPU), which contains the computer's arithmetic, logic, and control circuitry on an integrated circuit; two types of computer memory, main memory, such as digital random-access memory (RAM), and auxiliary memory, such as magnetic hard disks and special optical compact discs, or read-only memory (ROM) discs (CD-ROMs and DVD-ROMs); and various peripheral devices, including a display screen, keyboard and mouse, and printer.

5.1.2 PROCESSOR

A processor (CPU) is the logic circuitry that responds to and processes the basic instructions that drive a computer. The CPU is seen as the main and most crucial integrated circuitry (IC) chip in a computer, as it is responsible for interpreting most of computers commands. CPUs will perform most basic arithmetic, logic and I/O operations, as well as allocate commands for other chips and components running in a computer.

5.1.3 RAM

RAM is short for "random access memory" and while it might sound mysterious, RAM is one of the most fundamental elements of computing. RAM is the super-fast and temporary data storage space that a computer needs to access right now or in the next few moments.

5.2 Software

- **OS: Windows 10**
- **Compatible Browser**
- **Database Server**

5.2.1 Windows 10

Windows 10 is a Microsoft operating system for personal computers, tablets, embedded devices and internet of things devices.

Microsoft released Windows 10 in July 2015 as a follow-up to Windows 8. The company has said it will update Windows 10 in perpetuity rather than release a new, full-fledged operating system as a successor.

Anyone adopting Windows 10 can upgrade legacy machines directly from Windows 7 or Windows 8 to Windows 10 without re-imaging or performing intrusive and time-consuming system wipes and upgrade procedures. To upgrade from a previous version of Windows 10, IT or users run the Windows 10 OS installer, which transfers any applications and software on the previous OS, as well as settings and preferences over to Windows 10. Organizations and users can pick and choose how they will patch and update Windows 10. IT or users can access a Windows 10 upgrade through the Windows Update Assistant to manually begin an upgrade or wait for Windows Update to offer an upgrade when it is set to run.

Windows 10 features built-in capabilities that allow corporate IT departments to use mobile device management (MDM) software to secure and control devices running the operating system. In addition, organizations can use traditional desktop management software such as Microsoft System Center Configuration Manager.

Windows 10 Mobile is a version of the operating system Microsoft designed specifically for smartphones.

Windows 10 features

The familiar Start Menu, which Microsoft replaced with Live Tiles in Windows 8, returned in Windows 10. Users can still access Live Tiles and the touch-centric Metro interface from a panel on the right side of the Start Menu, however.

Windows 10's integrated search feature allows users to search all local locations, as well as the web simultaneously.

Microsoft Edge debuted with Windows 10 and replaces Internet Explorer as the default web browser. Edge includes tools such as Web Notes, which allows users to markup web sites, and Reading View, which allows users to view certain websites without the clutter

of ads. The browser integrates directly with Cortana, Microsoft's digital assistant, which is also embedded within Windows 10.

Cortana integrates directly with the Bing search engine and supports both text and voice input. It tracks and analyzes location services, communication history, email and text messages, speech and input personalization, services and applications, and browsing and search history in an effort to customize the OS experience to best suit users' needs. IT professionals can disable Cortana and some of its features with Group Policy settings.

Microsoft Windows 10 integrated support for multi factor authentication technologies, such as smartcards and tokens. In addition, Windows Hello brought biometric authentication to Windows 10, allowing users to log in with a fingerprint scan, iris scan or facial recognition technology.

The operating system also includes virtualization-based security tools such as Isolated User Mode, Windows Defender Device Guard and Windows Defender Credential Guard. These Windows 10 features keep data, processes and user credentials isolated in an attempt to limit the damage from any attacks.

Windows 10 also expanded support for BitLocker encryption to protect data in motion between users' devices, storage hardware, emails and cloud services.

The minimum Windows 10 Mobile hardware requirements for a smart phone are 1 GB RAM, 8 GB flash storage, a Trusted Platform Module, Unified Extensible Firmware Interface, 32 bits of color per pixel and 720p screen resolution Smartphones also require a Snapdragon SoC from Qualcomm Technologies.

Windows 10 upgrades

IT professionals and end users have two options to upgrade from Windows 7 or 8.1 to Windows 10. One is by installing and running the Get Windows 10 application. The other is to use an image file with a designated group of settings and applications to upgrade to Windows 10.

Windows 10 system requirements

The minimum Windows 10 hardware requirements for a PC or 2-in-1 device are:

- Processor: 1 gigahertz (GHz) or faster processor or system-on-a-chip (Soc)
- RAM: 1 gigabyte (GB) for 32-bit or 2 GB for 64-bit
- Hard disk space: 16 GB for 32-bit OS 20 GB for 64-bit OS
- Graphics card: DirectX 9 or later with Windows Display Driver Model 1.0
- Display: 800x600

When upgrading to Windows 10 from Windows XP, Microsoft only officially supports a clean install where nothing carries over from the previous OS. Application and hardware compatibility could be a problem with XP upgrades because the OS is so old.

Microsoft provides the Assessment and Planning Toolkit to help determine how ready existing systems and versions of Windows are for an upgrade. Windows 10 updates

There are four licensing structures, called branches, that dictate how and when Windows 10 devices receive updates.

5.2.2 Compatible Browser

Google Chrome is a cross-platform web browser developed by Google. It was first released in 2008 for Microsoft Windows, built with free software components from Apple WebKit and Mozilla Firefox. It was later ported to Linux, macOS, iOS, and Android, where it is the default browser. The browser is also the main component of Chrome OS, where it serves as the platform for web applications.

Functions of Web Browser

Our dependency on the Internet has massively increased. Stated below are functions of web browsers and how are they useful:

The main function is to retrieve information from the World Wide Web and making it available for users

Visiting any website can be done using a web browser. When a URL is entered in a browser, the web server takes us to that website

To run Java applets and flash content, plugins are available on the web browser

It makes Internet surfing easy as once we reach a website, we can easily check the hyperlinks and get more and more useful data online

Browsers use internal cache which gets stored and the user can open the same webpage time and again without losing extra data

Multiple webpages can be opened at the same time on a web browser

Options like back, forward, reload, stop reload, home, etc. are available on these web browsers, which make using them easy and convenient

5.2.3 MySQL Database Server

MySQL is one of the most recognizable technologies in the modern big data ecosystem. Often called the most popular database and currently enjoying widespread, effective use regardless of industry, it's clear that anyone involved with enterprise data or general IT should at least aim for a basic familiarity of MySQL.

With MySQL, even those new to relational systems can immediately build fast, powerful, and secure data storage systems. MySQL's programmatic syntax and interfaces are also perfect gateways into the wide world of other popular query languages and structured data stores.

MySQL is a relational database management system (RDBMS) developed by Oracle that is based on structured query language (SQL).

5.3 Language

- **HTML**
- **CSS**
- **PHP**
- **JS**

5.3.1 HTML

HTML, or HyperText Markup Language, allows web users to create and structure sections, paragraphs, and links using elements, tags, and attributes. However, it's worth noting that HTML is not considered a programming language as it can't create dynamic functionality.

5.3.2 CSS

Cascading Style Sheets (CSS) is a stylesheet language used to describe the presentation of a document written in HTML or XML (including XML dialects such as SVG, MathML or XHTML). CSS describes how elements should be rendered on screen, on paper, in speech, or on other media.

CSS is among the core languages of the open web and is standardized across Web browsers according to W3C specifications. Previously, development of various parts of CSS specification was done synchronously, which allowed versioning of the latest recommendations. You might have heard about CSS1, CSS2.1, CSS3. However, CSS4 has never become an official version.

5.3.3 PHP

The term PHP is an acronym for *PHP: Hypertext Preprocessor*. PHP is a server-side scripting language designed specifically for web development. It is open-source which means it is free to download and use. It is very simple to learn and use. The files have the extension “.php”.

Rasmus Lerdorf inspired the first version of PHP and participating in the later versions. It is an interpreted language and it does not require a compiler.

- PHP code is executed in the server.
- It can be integrated with many databases such as Oracle, Microsoft SQL Server, MySQL, PostgreSQL, Sybase, Informix.
- It is powerful to hold a content management system like WordPress and can be used to control user access.
- It supports main protocols like HTTP Basic, HTTP Digest, IMAP, FTP, and others.
- Websites like www.facebook.com, www.yahoo.com are also built on PHP.

5.3.4 JavaScript

JavaScript is a dynamic computer programming language. It is lightweight and most commonly used as a part of web pages, whose implementations allow client-side script to interact with the user and make dynamic pages. It is an interpreted programming language with object-oriented capabilities.

JavaScript was first known as LiveScript, but Netscape changed its name to JavaScript, possibly because of the excitement being generated by Java. JavaScript made its first appearance in Netscape 2.0 in 1995 with the name LiveScript. The general-purpose core of the language has been embedded in Netscape, Internet Explorer, and other web browsers.

The ECMA-262 Specification defined a standard version of the core JavaScript language.

- JavaScript is a lightweight, interpreted programming language.
- Designed for creating network-centric applications.
- Complementary to and integrated with Java.
- Complementary to and integrated with HTML.
- Open and cross-platform

CHAPTER 6

Design and Implementation

6.1 Introduction

This chapter explains the implementation phases of the system. Moreover, the implementation phase combines the requirements and design phase outputs and processes them using the appropriate technologies.

6.2 Analyze Phase

During the analysis phase, we determine the requirements of the project and get in touch with how we can improve the online marketplace's performance. We also determine how to implement the marketplaces needsto help them get professional work.

6.3 Build A Prototype

In this phase, the tools used in developing the prototype and the developed system are described:

6.3.1 Programming Tool

The system is developed using web development techniques (HTML5, CSS3, JavaScript, PHP) that let us design the system layout such as login form, tables, panels, and colors, then implement UI/UX elements such as: -

- Make the system easy to use.
- Make the system easy to learn.
- Choose the website colors carefully to enhance user interfaces
- Make the system device-friendly (mobile view, desktop view, etc.).

Then, make the system dynamic using programming tools (PHP v7, MySQL DBMS). It'll let us store the user's information in a database and view it through the WebPages using PHP v7.4.29.

6.4 Design Phase

During the design phase, the relationships between classes were designed and analyzed using the class diagram. After that, the database schema was developed to illustrate the mapping of the data.

6.5 Implementation Phase

After developing the databases of the system, the implementation phase emerges, and through this phase, several activities and techniques were used to develop the website as shown below. The development of the website starts with designing the website structure using HTML5. Then the style of the website was designed using CSS3. After that, enhanced user interfaces and dynamic websites were developed using JavaScript and jQuery. Later on, the website's contents and databases were managed through the use of PHP7.

Develop the website

- Design website structure using HTML5,
- Design styles of the website, including the design and layout using CSS3.
- Provide enhanced user interfaces and dynamic websites using JavaScript.
- Manage dynamic content, databases and session tracking using PHP v.7

6.6 User Interfaces

Admin Interface

Figure 9: Admin User Interface

Seller's Interface

Figure 10: Seller's User Interface

Gig Page Interface

Figure 11: Interface of gig page

Buyer's Interface

Figure 12: Buyer's User Interface

6.7 Conclusion

We had an explanation for the implementation phases of the system, which included the user interfaces, which have an admin interface, a seller's interface, buyer's interface, and an interface of gig page.

CHAPTER 7

Testing

7.1 Introduction

Web testing ensures you have an error free website by identifying issues and bugs that could potentially arise in your website before it goes live. To put it simple, Web testing includes testing various aspects of a web application to ensure proper functioning of the website.

This chapter illustrates the last phase of the project is the testing. In the testing phase, the performance testing and functionality testing performed.

7.2 Testing

Testing is an umbrella term for processes which test websites and other software applications for unwanted defects and issues across a broad range of devices. It includes functionality, usability, accessibility and performance testing.

Two types of testing were performed to test the website and how it supports mobile working. These tests were mainly performance testing and functionality testing.

7.2.1 Performance Testing

The website was tested on Google chrome browser using an online tool called GTMetrix, which analyzes web pages according to different rules by giving each rule a weigh, and then evaluate the score of each rule for the website. The rules tested by this tool are indicated below.

- Make fewer HTTP requests
- Remove duplicate JavaScript and CSS
- Use a CDN
- Configure ETags
- Avoid empty src or href
- Use cookie-free domains
- Avoid HTTP 404 (Not Found) error
- Add Expires headers
- Use cookie-free domains
- Avoid URL redirects
- Reduce DNS lookups
- Avoid AlphaImageLoader filter etc.

7.2.2 Functionality Testing

Functional testing checks an application, website, or system to ensure that it is doing exactly what it is meant to. Functionality testing of a Website is a process that includes several testing parameters like user interface, APIs, database testing, security testing, client and server testing and basic website functionalities. Functional testing is very convenient and it allows users to perform both manual and automated testing.

Security Testing

Security Testing is vital for e-commerce website that store sensitive customer information like credit cards. Testing Activities will include-

- Test unauthorized access to secure pages should not be permitted
- Restricted files should not be downloadable without appropriate access
- Check sessions are automatically killed after prolonged user inactivity
- On use of SSL certificates, website should re-direct to encrypted SSL pages.

Tools that can be used: Babel Enterprise, BFBTester and CROSS

Database Testing

Database is one critical component of your web application and stress must be laid to test it thoroughly. Testing activities will include-

- Test if any errors are shown while executing queries
- Data Integrity is maintained while creating, updating or deleting data in the database.
- Check response time of queries and fine tune them if necessary.
- Test data retrieved from your database is shown accurately in your web application

Tools that can be used: QTP, Selenium

Interface Testing

Three areas to be tested here are – Application, Web and Database Server

Application: Test requests are sent correctly to the Database and output at the client side is displayed correctly. Errors if any must be caught by the application and must be only shown to the administrator and not the end user. Web Server: Test Web server is handling all application requests without any service denial. Database Server: Make sure queries sent to the database give expected results.

Chapter 8

Conclusion and Upcoming Features

8.1 Conclusion

For last few years, Freelancing is being more popular among people. Specially after covid-19, it has become a demanding as people can work from any side of the world. It is a revolutionary thing. It will increase the remittance of the country as the freelancer will be able to work internationally.

8.2 Upcoming Features

In future we can add some advance features that may help to improve the system and get more popularity. These features can be summarized in the following points:

- Sellers can offer subscription base services
- Seller's will be able to sell premade design's which will be customizable.
- Seller's and buyer's will be able to pay or withdraw through Mobile Banking system.

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